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Abstract:	This document provides updated information on how the project has connected with its stakeholders through various channels, such as the SmartCHANGE.eu website, social media, events, and publications. The document also reports on quantitative and qualitative measures demonstrating the impact of the project.
Keyword List:	Artificial Intelligence & Decision support, chronic diseases, risk assessment, children, youth, long-term risk prediction, chronic NCD, behaviour change, artificial intelligence, federated learning, explainable AI, robustness, bias, participatory design, proof-of-concept study
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Executive summary

This midterm deliverable provides an overview of communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities carried out during the first half of the SmartCHANGE project, alongside a forward-looking strategy for the remainder of the project.

Over the initial 24 months, communication and dissemination have focused on building the project's identity, increasing its visibility, and engaging key audiences in research, healthcare, and policy. A consistent visual identity was developed early on and applied across a range of digital and printed materials. The project website, social media accounts, and newsletter infrastructure have all been launched and continuously updated. SmartCHANGE has participated in multiple events—both as a contributor and organiser—and has begun publishing peer-reviewed research in relevant journals and conferences.

Dissemination efforts have so far concentrated primarily on **academic audiences, health professionals, and policymakers**. These groups have been targeted through scientific papers, institutional networks, conference participation, and the establishment of synergies with sister projects and relevant initiatives. At the same time, strong foundations have been laid for the wider communication of the project to the general public. This includes the creation of multimedia content (e.g. interviews, animations, and explainers), the opening of an Instagram account to reach youth and families, and preparation for more public-facing campaigns in the second half of the project.

Looking ahead, SmartCHANGE will ramp up its outreach to **families, educators, and children**—the stakeholders at the centre of the project's long-term vision. This will involve co-design stories, Healthy Lifestyle Tours, video content, interactive exhibitions, and school-based engagement. Dissemination will also expand to include the promotion of the SmartCHANGE mobile and web applications as they become available, alongside the continued publication of results related to federated learning, explainable AI, ethical data use, and behaviour change interventions.

This document outlines both the progress made and the strategic direction that will guide SmartCHANGE's communication and dissemination activities toward maximum visibility, inclusiveness, and impact.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation
DEM	Digital Engagement Manager
EBA	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EHTEL	European Health Telematics Association
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENG	Engineering Ingegneria Informatica Spa
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FL	Federated learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HELT	Health Law and Technology
HL7	Health Level 7
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

ML	Machine learning
NCD	Non-Communicable Disease
ODbL	Open Database License
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
OSS	Open-source software
SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
TUE	Eindhoven University of Technology
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Centre
USI	Università della Svizzera Italiana
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work package
XAI	Explainable artificial intelligence

1 Introduction

Effective communication and dissemination are central to ensuring that the SmartCHANGE project achieves broad impact of its results. Communication efforts aim to raise awareness among key stakeholders, policymakers, and the public about the importance of early intervention for non-communicable diseases (NCDs) through AI-powered, youth-focused tools. Dissemination activities actively engage end users—such as healthcare professionals, educators, and families—who will benefit from and apply SmartCHANGE’s solutions. The project also promotes collaboration and uptake by researchers and institutions through scientific publications, conferences, and synergies with other European initiatives. By maintaining open access to results and transparent communication of activities, SmartCHANGE demonstrates accountability in the use of EU funding. Furthermore, communication and dissemination activities contribute to the long-term sustainability of SmartCHANGE outcomes by building a strong stakeholder network and promoting integration of the tools into healthcare and educational systems beyond the project’s duration.

As the project reaches its midterm point, its public-facing efforts have matured considerably. Over the past 24 months, SmartCHANGE has moved from conceptualisation to implementation. Communication activities have focused on building awareness, establishing a recognisable brand, and cultivating an initial stakeholder community. Meanwhile, dissemination has centred on positioning SmartCHANGE within scientific, technical, and policy landscapes, primarily through publications, events, and direct engagement with expert stakeholders.

At this stage, SmartCHANGE has laid the groundwork for deeper engagement. The dissemination of scientific outputs has grown steadily, with multiple peer-reviewed publications and conference contributions already achieved. Engagement with health professionals and policymakers has been pursued through events, webinars, and focused dialogue around the ethical and regulatory dimensions of AI in health. Dedicated branding, an evolving web presence, and early adoption of video content have also supported the visibility of the project.

SmartCHANGE is ultimately a project for people—especially children, families, and educators. These groups have not yet been the primary focus of communication efforts, but they will be central in the coming months. With the beginning of outreach activities such as healthy lifestyle tours and feasibility studies on the horizon, the project is now entering a phase in which public outreach, storytelling, and accessible communication will become increasingly

critical. To this end, new channels such as Instagram are being introduced, and strategies for participatory engagement are taking shape.

This deliverable reflects on the tools and tactics used so far, presents measurable outcomes from the first 24 months, and outlines how the SmartCHANGE communication and dissemination strategy will evolve to meet the needs of broader, more diverse audiences—ensuring the project remains transparent, inclusive, and impactful throughout its lifecycle.

2 Dissemination and Communication objectives

The SmartCHANGE project maintains a comprehensive strategy for dissemination, communication, and exploitation to maximise its scientific, social, and commercial impact. Building upon the foundation established in [D8.2] (Initial Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan, M3), this midterm report [D8.3] reflects the progress achieved during the first 24 months and outlines refined approaches for the remaining project duration.

Our stakeholder engagement framework, detailed in Section 3, shows the project's ecosystem: the SmartCHANGE AI platform, with its privacy-secured data architecture and predictive models, serves as the technical core. This directly supports healthcare professionals through risk prediction and recommendation tools, who in turn engage with families and youth (5-25 years old) through our participatory design approach. This multi-layered interaction drives awareness and behavioural change while generating valuable feedback for continuous improvement.

The SmartCHANGE project has implemented a coordinated strategy across all dimensions of knowledge transfer. Our communication efforts revolve around the project website as a central hub, complemented by active social media engagement on LinkedIn, X (Twitter), and YouTube channels. Regular newsletters extend our reach to broader audiences, ensuring both specialist and general public awareness of project developments.

For dissemination activities, we prioritise direct engagement with professional communities through conference participation and open-access publications, archived both through traditional publisher platforms and our Zenodo repository. An Editorial Board maintains an overview over scientific outputs, while our growing collection of multimedia materials and interactive tools enhances accessibility for general audiences.

3 Assessment of target stakeholders

An effective stakeholder engagement strategy is essential to ensure that SmartCHANGE delivers real impact. The project targets a broad range of stakeholder groups, each with different motivations, channels of influence, and expectations. As such, the communication and dissemination approach are intentionally flexible, adapting to stakeholder needs, project developments, and emerging opportunities over time.

The primary target groups were initially identified as researchers, health professionals, policymakers, educators, children and youth, and families. Engagement efforts to date have been uneven across these groups, reflecting the natural progression of project activities. Researchers, health professionals, and policymakers have been the most actively engaged so far, while actions targeting children, youth, educators, and families will intensify in the second half of the project with the rollout of public-facing tools.

Engagement with **researchers** has followed the pathway outlined in D8.2, primarily through scientific dissemination activities. SmartCHANGE researchers have participated in conferences, workshops, and academic collaborations, publishing scientific articles in AI, healthcare, and ethics fields. We have also ensured that results are open access and promoted in relevant research communities. The value proposition to researchers remains the contribution of new models, methods, and datasets for the advancement of research in AI-based health prediction.

Health professionals are another crucial group, as they will ultimately be users or endorsers of SmartCHANGE's tools in real-world settings. The project offers them decision support systems, best practices for lifestyle guidance, and clarity on evidence-based recommendations. Health professionals have been involved through workshops, participatory design sessions, and consultations, ensuring their needs directly influence the development of the web and mobile applications. SmartCHANGE places strong emphasis on transparency and interpretability, and will continue refining the user experience and communication materials in this direction.

With **policymakers**, the focus has been on highlighting how SmartCHANGE can support preventive health policies through population-level risk assessments and practical recommendations. Engagement with this group has benefitted from the relevance of the AI Act and regulatory debates around AI in healthcare. The project has already started participating in dialogues linked to health policy, data privacy, and the regulation of AI-powered health technologies. Policymakers are offered insights into the safe and ethical use

of AI in preventive healthcare, as well as recommendations that can support broader adoption at national and European levels.

While this initial phase of the project has prioritised institutional and expert stakeholders, limited engagement has so far been carried out with children and youth, families, and educators—who are equally critical to the long-term success of SmartCHANGE. These groups are the direct beneficiaries of the tools being developed, particularly the mobile app and educational materials. However, reaching them requires different methods and messaging than for scientific or policy communities.

SmartCHANGE recognises the need for more playful, intuitive, and accessible formats to engage these audiences. The value proposition for children and youth lies in developing good health habits in a way that is fun and engaging. For families, SmartCHANGE can offer meaningful support in guiding their children toward healthier behaviours. For educators, the project provides validated materials that fit within their broader educational objectives, such as fostering physical well-being and digital literacy.

In the next phase, we will scale up our efforts toward these groups. A SmartCHANGE Instagram account has been created and will launch in conjunction with the May General Assembly, with visual content, health challenges, and community-driven posts designed to resonate with younger users and parents alike. Public-facing events, collaborations with schools, and multimedia content (including animations and video interviews, already available on the YouTube channel) will be key tools in making the project more visible and relevant to the general public.

While each group requires its own approach, synergies between stakeholders are actively pursued—for example, through educators who act as bridges to both families and youth, or health professionals who connect research outputs with practical implementation. In future phases, participatory activities like workshops and pilot testing will also create valuable feedback loops across stakeholder categories.

Beyond these primary groups, SmartCHANGE has also laid important groundwork with industry stakeholders, international institutions, and standardisation bodies. While these are considered secondary stakeholders, they play a strategic role in scaling, sustainability, and uptake beyond the lifetime of the project. The project's open architecture, modular design, and adherence to international standards create clear value propositions for SMEs, startups, and larger HealthTech companies, who may adopt, adapt, or build upon SmartCHANGE technologies. Outreach has included mapping potential actors and initiating

contacts, with more targeted activities planned in the next phases—particularly as prototypes mature. Likewise, international networks and professional societies, such as the International Society of Behavioural Nutrition and Physical Activity, are being engaged for the dissemination of best practices and findings. Finally, efforts are ongoing to identify relevant standardisation bodies in the fields of digital health and AI in medicine (e.g., HL7, CEN/CENELEC, EMA), where SmartCHANGE can contribute practical insights and possibly shape emerging standards—particularly around explainability, federated learning, and AI-based risk prediction in preventive health.

This evolving, segmented strategy ensures that SmartCHANGE is not only producing valuable knowledge and tools but also building relationships and momentum among those who will help bring these innovations into everyday use.

4 Communication and Dissemination Activities

The SmartCHANGE communication strategy follows a **SMART** (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound) and KPI-driven framework to support community building, stakeholder engagement, and visibility of project outcomes. Over the first half of the project, this strategy has moved from planning to active delivery, with communication and dissemination efforts evolving in step with project milestones. A multichannel approach—anchored in the project website, social media, newsletters, publications, and events—continues to be applied and adapted to the needs of both expert and public audiences. The following sections detail the activities carried out to date and outline how SmartCHANGE will expand its reach in the second half of the project.

4.1 SmartCHANGE project communication

This communication strategy addresses all stakeholders (see Section 0) and aims to strengthen the project's positioning across different audience groups.

4.1.1 Branding and communication kit

The branding assets are categorised into physical and digital materials.

- **Digital materials:** Social media banners, newsletter templates, Zoom backgrounds, and PowerPoint slides (customisable as needed).
- **Physical materials:** Promotional items for events, including tote bags, step counters, flyers, stickers, and health-related gadgets (e.g., toothbrushes, training elastics) that have been tested during consortium meetings and deployed at project events. See Figure 2.

Most of the digital branding resources are available for download in the Communication Kit on the project website. This kit includes logo packs, roll-up banners, posters & leaflets, and press releases.

Additionally, the project maintains and produces a suite of social media branded content, all created and hosted on Figma, together with the digital versions of the other resources.

4.1.2 Website

The SmartCHANGE website (<http://www.smart-change.eu>) serves as the project's central digital hub, providing a structured, user-friendly platform for disseminating information and engaging stakeholders. Functioning as both an information repository and community portal, the website offers:

- Regularly updated news and event announcements
- Critical resources for key stakeholders (policy makers, educators, researchers, and families)
- Newsletter subscription
- Community engagement tools
- Future access to the SmartCHANGE App

The second version of the SmartCHANGE website (Figure 3), which brought a revamp of the main page and the addition of new pages, was launched in M6 (October 2023). Aside from a partial restructuring of information in the homepage (removal of objectives and proof of concept, addition of a What's New slider and Quote slider), this version presented the following new pages:

Homepage redesign:

- Implemented a dynamic "What's New" content slider
- Added an inspirational quote slider feature
- Streamlined content presentation by removing redundant sections
- Improved visual hierarchy and user pathways

New content sections:

- 1) About section**
 - a. Detailed project mission statement and methodological approach
 - b. Partner consortium information
 - c. Video gallery (integrated with SmartCHANGE YouTube channel)
 - d. Communication Kit with downloadable branding assets
- 2) Objectives section**
 - a. Comprehensive presentation of project goals
 - b. Detailed expected impacts from successful implementation
- 3) Proof of Concept section (to be updated in Feasibility Studies)**
 - a. Visual and textual presentation of four planned validation studies

- b. Study designs and expected outcomes
- 4) News section
 - a. Chronologically organised project updates
 - b. Archive functionality for historical content
- 5) Events section
 - a. Calendar interface for project-related events
 - b. Integration of relevant third-party activities
- 6) Contact section
 - a. User inquiry form with categorisation options
 - b. Project contact information

Figure 3: Overview of the new pages present in the updated version of the website

Ongoing website enhancements have been carried out and have focused on improving user experience and content richness:

1. **Interactive timeline:** visual representation of project milestones and events with direct links to related content. See Figure 4.

2. **Synergies page:** dedicated section for aligned EU-funded projects with project descriptions and collaboration opportunities. See Section 4.4 for detailed synergies analysis and Figure 4.
3. **Newsletter issues:** repository with all the newsletters dispatched by the project. See Section 4.1.4 for further details on the newsletter.
4. **Outputs & Documents:** centralised access to project deliverables, reports, publications, and conference materials with automatic synchronisation with SmartCHANGE Zenodo website. See Section 4.2 for details on SmartCHANGE results dissemination.
5. **External Advisory Board:** section showcasing SmartCHANGE three international experts specialising in NCDs and Machine Learning applications in health research, providing strategic guidance to the project. See Figure 4.

Figure 4: New pages on the website (newsletter issues, EAB, timeline, and synergy pages)

The SmartCHANGE website will undergo strategic enhancements throughout the project lifecycle to become an increasingly dynamic and user-focused platform. These planned improvements will be implemented through ongoing collaboration with our technical partners and continuous integration of stakeholder feedback. Key focus areas for future developments will include enhanced interactivity and user engagement features, improved content organisation and accessibility, and seamless integration with project tools and resources, including the integration of the SmartCHANGE apps once available, as well as harmonising the web application with the project website and connecting the two via a highlighted gateway (see also Table 1).

This evolutionary approach ensures the website remains aligned with user needs while effectively showcasing project outcomes.

Table 1: Website KPI monitoring

Action line	KPI to monitor	M25	M48
Website	Project website: overall sessions	140	500 per month

4.1.3 Social media

The SmartCHANGE project has developed a dynamic, multi-platform social media strategy designed to serve as the digital hub connecting the consortium and its growing community of stakeholders. This strategy is designed to address three key communication goals: raising broad awareness of the project's vision and objectives, encouraging active engagement in its activities and events, and driving the adoption of the SmartCHANGE web and mobile applications among target user groups.

Social media outreach primarily focuses on the project's LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), and YouTube channels (Figure 5). Our social media strategy revolves around these platforms, each selected for its unique strengths within our broader communication ecosystem.

LinkedIn serves as our flagship professional channel, where we maintain a strong institutional presence through our company page while fostering an organic, engaged network. The platform has proven highly effective for interactions within the professional ecosystem, allowing us to share articles, connect with researchers, healthcare professionals, and policy stakeholders, and promote one of our newsletters (see Section 4.1.4 for more details). As of M24, the SmartCHANGE LinkedIn page has 272 followers, and the platform has become indispensable for promoting webinars, events, and project-related news. Its robust community-building features continue to support the steady expansion of a targeted and highly engaged professional audience.

The project's presence on **X (formerly Twitter)** addresses the need for rapid information dissemination and real-time engagement, despite the platform's evolving challenges. We've adapted our approach here to emphasise visual content sharing, strategic use of health-tech related hashtags, and live coverage during major project events. However, due to the platform's shifting landscape and declining popularity among some user groups, we are currently assessing whether to maintain our presence or transition to a more suitable alternative based on stakeholder engagement and relevance.

Our **YouTube** channel serves as the project's visual storytelling hub, hosting an expanding library of interview content, webinar recordings, and explanatory videos. The channel currently has 11 subscribers and it hosts 14 videos published to date, with over 800 views. Particularly noteworthy is our interview series, recorded during the project's kick-off meeting, which features representation across Work Packages, partner institutions, and gender.

There is a KPI specifically for the production of promotional videos for the project. See Table 2.

Table 2 - Video-related KPI monitoring

Action line	KPI to monitor	M24	M48
YouTube	Promotional Videos	14	15

Additionally, SmartCHANGE is in the process of launching an **Instagram** account to broaden its audience reach and visual storytelling capacity.

Figure 5: SmartCHANGE social media cover pages (X, LinkedIn, YouTube)

As of April 2025, the SmartCHANGE social media community includes over 330 followers, primarily on LinkedIn. The YouTube channel is embedded and promoted through the website and other social platforms, while the project’s presence on X continues despite challenges inherent to the platform. As project results become available, the community is expected to grow significantly in 2025 (Table 3).

Table 3 - Social media KPI monitoring

Action line	KPI to monitor	M24	M48
Social media	Overall SmartCHANGE community (Number of contacts, including registered users, social media, event participants, etc)	435	3000

Looking ahead, we are implementing several strategic enhancements to our social media presence. The imminent launch of an Instagram account will allow us to engage younger demographics and experiment with more visual storytelling formats. We're also developing a structured schedule for paid promotional campaigns to coincide with major project milestones. Our video production pipeline will expand to include testimonials, application walkthroughs, and progress update series.

SmartCHANGE is analysing its presence on X, exploring new platforms to better align with stakeholder preferences. Given the evolving landscape on X, the communication team, alongside partners, is assessing whether to maintain or shift to alternative platforms based on audience engagement and relevance.

This comprehensive social media strategy directly supports our overarching goal of building a 3000-member SmartCHANGE community, with each platform contributing unique value to this collective effort.

4.1.4 Newsletters

SmartCHANGE newsletters serve as a bridge between the project and its growing community of stakeholders. Since the project's start, we have developed a comprehensive newsletter strategy that delivers timely updates through two primary channels: **direct email newsletters** and **LinkedIn newsletters**.

A newsletter contact form has been implemented on the website since M1, to start building up a community database of interested people. The collection of these contacts complies with the GDPR and the project's Privacy Policy.

At the time of writing, SmartCHANGE has successfully built a base of 89 active subscribers on MailJet, the tool used for direct email newsletters. The three editions distributed to date have demonstrated strong engagement metrics, achieving a 66.67% open rate and a 54.59% click-through rate. These newsletters feature website-related content, including project milestones, event announcements, partner contributions, and relevant community opportunities. All newsletter issues dispatched through direct email remain accessible through a dedicated section on the SmartCHANGE website, as mentioned in Section 4.1.2.

Parallel to our direct email efforts, the LinkedIn newsletter campaigns have expanded our reach to 120 professional subscribers. The three editions published on this platform have generated substantial visibility with 1,315 impressions, 173 article views and 44 engagements. Audience analytics reveal our content resonates particularly with

professionals in research services (18.2%), higher education (14%), and IT/consulting sectors (11.6%), along with significant interest from **software development (9.1%) and healthcare professionals (8.3%).**

The newsletter *per se* does not have a dedicated KPI; however, it contributes significantly to our broader objective of cultivating a 3,000-member SmartCHANGE community. Further details on SmartCHANGE's community database are highlighted in Section 4.5. The consistently strong engagement metrics across both distribution channels validate our content strategy and inform ongoing refinements to maximise impact.

The newsletter is already a well-established communication channel. Moving forward, we will strengthen our newsletter strategy through three key priorities: first, expanding subscriber acquisition through targeted campaigns and partner networks to grow our community base. Second, enhancing content relevance and third, developing more interactive newsletter formats featuring multimedia elements.

4.1.5 Press releases

The SmartCHANGE project has implemented a structured press release strategy to communicate major developments to both specialist and general audiences. The first press release, published in June 2023 (M1) following the project's kick-off meeting, was made available in English on the project website. To support regional outreach, it was translated into Slovenian and Finnish, and disseminated through local partner networks.

These press materials serve as valuable outreach tools despite not being tied to specific KPIs, enabling us to reach audiences beyond our standard communication channels. The consortium has established distribution pathways through media contacts, partner institutions, and project communication platforms to maximise visibility.

Looking ahead, the project will adopt a strategic approach to press releases by considering their publication following important project achievements. These may include key milestones such as the development of the apps, significant research breakthroughs, major events, or other notable accomplishments. All press materials will continue to be archived in the project's Communication Kit, ensuring partners have access to approved content for their dissemination activities.

4.2 SmartCHANGE results dissemination

Dissemination of results in SmartCHANGE is an ongoing and evolving process aimed at promoting knowledge-sharing and increasing visibility of the project. This primarily includes participation in conferences and publishing results in scientific journals, though policy briefs and white papers can also prove to be important in later stages of the project. These activities can and have been undertaken not just by the project as an individual, but also from a joint cluster perspective.

LinkedIn has been continuously used to build and engage a solid community of key stakeholders, while publication of results has been made FAIR through the use of Github and Zenodo. The project has created an Instagram account (ready for M24), with initial posts being prepared around the upcoming General Assembly in May, which will serve as a launching point. Our dissemination approach will also have to include hands-on, interactive outreach through partnerships with museums & sports centres, where competitions and awareness campaigns will be further promoted using Instagram to showcase Lifestyle Champions as well as SmartCHANGE use in real-world settings.

4.2.1 Dissemination of research outputs

Dissemination channels include both AI and health-related conferences and journals, reflecting the multidisciplinary scope of the project. To broaden awareness, we continue to explore health-focused events and collaborations guided by our health partners.

Research outputs have been central to SmartCHANGE dissemination. We have actively participated in multiple conferences and published in various academic journals, both of which are tracked in an online file which the entire consortium can monitor and report in. Full details of these events are included in the Events section of this deliverable, while the currently published publications can be found in the Table 4.

Table 4 – List of current project publications

Title of the publication	Partner	Title of the journal or conference
SmartCHANGE: AI-based long-term health risk evaluation for driving behaviour change strategies in children and youth	ALL	2023 International Conference on Applied Mathematics & Computer Science (ICAMCS)
Federated Learning for Privacy-aware Cognitive Workload Estimation	USI	MUM '23: Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia

A Federated Unsupervised Personalisation for Cognitive Workload Estimation	USI	MUM '23: Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia
A Cross-Sector Data Space for Correlating Environmental Risks with Human Health	UPRC	European, Mediterranean, and Middle Eastern Conference on Information Systems (EMCIS) 2023
Federated Behavioural Planes: Explaining the Evolution of Client Behaviour in Federated Learning	USI	NeurIPS 2024
Multi-Frequency Federated Learning for Human Activity Recognition Using Head-Worn Sensors	USI	International Conference on Intelligent Environments 2024
AnyCBMs: How to Turn Any Black Box into a Concept Bottleneck Model	USI	XAI World Conference 2024 - Late-breaking works (Workshop)
Subgroup Harm Assessor: Identifying Potential Fairness-Related Harms and Predictive Bias	TUE	Joint European Conference on Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases
A Data Modeling Process for Achieving Interoperability	UPRC	International Conference on e-Health and Bioengineering (EHB) 2023
SmartCHANGE Risk Prediction Tool: Demonstrating Risk Assessment for Children and Youth	JSI	Information Society 2024
Post-event report	Trust+VUB	AI in Healthcare: The AI Act and other Regulatory Issues
SmartCHANGE: Long-Term Health Risk Prediction for Children and Youth	JSI	KDD2024
Health Risk Prediction for Children Built on a Combination of Heterogeneous Datasets	JSI	16th International Conference ETAI 2024
Addressing Complex Data Integration and Harmonization Scenarios	UPRC	International Conference on e-Health and Bioengineering (EHB) 2024
SmartCHANGE: AI-based long-term health risk evaluation for driving behaviour change strategies in children and youth	ALL	2023 International Conference on Applied Mathematics & Computer Science (ICAMCS)
Federated Learning for Privacy-aware Cognitive Workload Estimation	USI	MUM '23: Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia

In line with our commitment to open science, all peer-reviewed publications have been and will continue to be made openly accessible—either via the publisher’s link or deposited in the project’s Zenodo repository—and can be found on the SmartCHANGE website.

Additionally, the project has established an Editorial Board that meets quarterly to supervise and discuss upcoming publication opportunities and ideas. The list of upcoming publications that was outlined during the latest call, in March 2025 is outlined in Table 5 below:

Table 5 – List of upcoming project publications

Authors	Topic	Expected Release
VUMC (+ other health partners)	Co-design protocol	Q3-Q4 2025
UPRC	Comparative study on data cleaning processes	Q3-Q4 2025
USI	Technical papers in progress (FL, XAI)	Q3-Q4 2025
JSI	Paper for BHI conference	May 2025
USI + TUE	Paper on their shared work (XAI)	Q3-Q4 2025
USI + JSI	Paper on their shared work (ML to FL)	Q3-Q4 2025
CCARE	Concept development of the Happy Plant App	Q3-Q4 2025
VUMC + other health partners	Process evaluation paper regarding implementation of co-design protocol in 4 countries	Q3-Q4 2025
VUMC + JAMK	Perspectives of adolescents on their health: comparison Finland & the Netherlands	Q3-Q4 2025
VUMC + health partners	Realist review of e-/m-Health interventions	Q3-Q4 2025

SmartCHANGE also shares code and tools developed through the project where possible. Implementations of AI methods deemed reusable or broadly applicable are being prepared for publication in open-source repositories such as GitHub. A major dataset will be collected, and any privacy-compliant subset will be shared via Zenodo and described in a corresponding publication.

Instruments for research-oriented dissemination in SmartCHANGE include:

- **Open-source software (OSS):** Most academic developments are shared via GitHub using business-friendly licenses (e.g., MPL/LGPL).
- **Open and FAIR data:** Our public Data Management Plan [D1.2] outlines how data is documented, stored, and shared. Anonymised datasets are made available via FAIR repositories and follow interoperability standards such as HL7 FHIR and OMOP. Data licenses like ODbL will be used where applicable. Models and workflows will be shared via repositories like OpenML, and we plan to offer at least one service through EOSC.
- **Trial registration:** The proof-of-concept study has been registered in the EU Clinical Trials Register. Protocol amendments and results will be updated accordingly.

4.2.2 Principal project assets for dissemination

While a full discussion of the project's assets is presented in the separate Exploitation deliverable, this section touches on how the main assets of the project are currently contributing to dissemination.

The primary two outputs, which are the **Mobile App for citizens** and the **Web App for health professionals**, will serve as major vectors for dissemination once available. Currently, dissemination has primarily focused on other key outputs such as research on machine learning, federated learning, data harmonisation, ethical and legal guidelines, and health-related studies.

Open-source software outputs from these areas, including tools for data harmonisation, are being documented and will be made available as sustainable, exploitable, and disseminable assets. The precise nature of these tools will continue to emerge through ongoing R&D and once the Exploitation plan has been delivered.

Results from our feasibility studies will be further disseminated through targeted webinars, trainings, and event participation, with documented best practices aimed at clinicians, health workers, families, and the broader public

4.2.3 New media and multimedia (educational material)

Narrative storytelling remains a cornerstone of our dissemination strategy. We consistently produce and promote written content—including blogs, articles, and editorial content—enriched with visual elements (see Figure 6: Two of the SmartCHANGE IllustrationsFigure 6), These materials are strategically promoted for general and specific (e.g. in parallel with

results or events) visibility. In parallel, we have created video interviews and recordings, which are available on the project's YouTube channel.

An informative video on AI was produced on behalf of the Health Partners for internal use.

Looking ahead, we aim to expand our use of visual content—such as short animations and GIFs— to increase engagement and visibility, especially via the new Instagram channel. These multimedia elements will complement our storytelling efforts and help further disseminate project outputs in accessible and appealing formats to our target audiences.

Figure 6: Two of the SmartCHANGE Illustrations for presentations

4.3 Events

The SmartCHANGE project has developed a comprehensive event strategy that leverages the consortium's extensive experience in knowledge dissemination to foster dialogue with stakeholders. SmartCHANGE events serve multiple purposes: raising public awareness about NCD prevention, facilitating the adoption of project results, and establishing pathways for long-term sustainability and exploitation. The event strategy includes the organisation of 10 workshops, plus 4 training sessions and participation in third-party events (up to 30).

Specific and dedicated promotional campaigns, including creation of web pages, customised social media promotion, distribution of dissemination materials, and support to logistics, have been set up and run both for SmartCHANGE-organised events and for third-party events where SmartCHANGE was promoted.

The aim is to solidly position the project inside the international AI and health ecosystem, with a clear dissemination plan. All project events are tracked in a shared consortium spreadsheet to ensure coordination and visibility. As of M24, SmartCHANGE has organised five events — including internal consortium meetings — and participated in 20 third-party events, strengthening its presence and engagement across the European ecosystem.

4.3.1 SmartCHANGE events

Throughout its lifecycle, the SmartCHANGE project is organising a series of targeted events, each tailored to engage specific stakeholder groups, achieve defined objectives, and deliver measurable outputs. Work Package 8 (WP8) is responsible for ensuring comprehensive support for every event, following a structured four-phase cycle:

1. **Preparation:** Agenda development, speaker engagement, creation of event webpages, and registration procedures.
2. **Promotion:** Targeted outreach through social media campaigns, press coverage, and dissemination via the Digital Engagement Manager (DEM).
3. **Execution:** Logistical support and real-time engagement, including live social media coverage.
4. **Follow-up:** Coordination of post-event reporting, summary production, and promotion of outcomes and related materials.

Events may be held in either virtual or in-person formats, depending on feasibility and target audience needs. The first event was the face-to-face consortium Kick-Off Meeting, in Ljubljana (Slovenia). At the time of writing, SmartCHANGE held two consortium meetings and two **webinars**. The first webinar, held in July 2024, was a joint initiative with sister projects AI4HF and DataTools4Heart, exploring the ethical and legal implications of the AI Act in healthcare. The session drew strong interest, with over 130 registrations. The second webinar, in November 2024, focused on the co-design process for healthcare tools, featuring insights and best practices from designers and researchers involved in SmartCHANGE. This session attracted more than 45 registrants.

Professional and policy-maker workshops. Interactive workshops will target not only citizens, but also health professionals. The consortium will demonstrate the use of the SmartCHANGE application, explain its background, and show how it can help them in their work. As with citizens, the consortium will leverage testimonials, experiences and lessons learned from the participatory design and the proof-of-concept studies.

As already mentioned in Section 0, the **Healthy Lifestyle Tours** aim to raise awareness around the links between lifestyle habits and non-communicable diseases (NCDs), and highlight the role of predictive tools in prevention. These in-person events will be hosted at science museums located in partner countries participating in the PoC studies. Each tour will be tailored to the project's timeline, with content and activities aligned to different phases of development and community engagement.

While initial events have seen modest attendance, we anticipate increased engagement as concrete results emerge from proof-of-concept studies. Future plans include enhanced coordination on event participation and organisation with sister projects (see Section 4.4 for synergies) and strategic timing of events to coincide with major project milestones.

4.3.2 Third-party events

The SmartCHANGE consortium actively leverages its partners' extensive professional networks to maximise project visibility and impact through strategic participation in third-party events. As the project evolves, consortium members will be able to arrange for presentations and workshops associated with these events. The third-party events are the ideal platform to disseminate the project results and also to promote further activities.

A key example of our strategic engagement is the annual HELT Symposium (*Health Law and Technology*) hosted by partner VUB. Building on our successful 2024 participation, where researchers from Università della Svizzera Italiana represented SmartCHANGE, the project is having an even more substantial presence in the 2025 symposium. This year's involvement features a collaborative effort between Amsterdam University Medical Centre, Eindhoven Technical University, and Vrije Universiteit Brussel to host a dedicated workshop session. This interactive forum will bring together legal experts, healthcare professionals, and AI specialists to examine the complex interplay between regulatory frameworks and innovative technological solutions for global health challenges.

As a further example, consortium partner ENG is a member of EHTEL¹, which organises numerous periodic events, and may have the opportunity to arrange for presentations and working slots within appropriate events organised by this entity.

Looking ahead, we have implemented a systematic approach to third-party event participation, targeting at least one major external engagement per quarter. This rhythm

¹ <https://ehtel.eu/>

ensures consistent visibility while allowing for thoughtful preparation of effective contributions. All third-party events are tracked in a shared consortium spreadsheet to ensure coordination and visibility, and WP8 works closely with partners to identify events that align with project milestones. Current efforts focus on securing speaking slots at venues that will be most receptive to our proof-of-concept results as they emerge, while also cultivating relationships with potential adopters of the SmartCHANGE applications.

There are several KPIs specifically for event organisation and participation (Table 6).

Table 6 - Events KPI monitoring

Action line	KPI to monitor	M24	M48
Organisation of conferences/workshops	10 events (physical) with 150 visitors, including 2 demo days for non-specialised audiences	1	10
Common events with affiliated projects	4 events (physical, as part of the above category) organised with affiliated projects	1	4
Third-party events	Attendance at 30 third-party conferences/workshops (online or physical)	20	30
Online webinars	4 online webinars directed to the general public, with 80 attendees	2	4
Training sessions	4 training sessions organised by the academic partners	1	4

4.4 Synergies, clustering, and collaboration

Maximising the results of Communication and Dissemination efforts necessarily requires the establishment of relevant synergies and clusters. The SmartCHANGE project has taken the lead in creating the Stay Healthy Cluster, which brings it together with six other projects funded the same call: AI-PROGNOSIS, AI-POD, AI4HF, DT4H, STRATIFYHF and TRUSTroke. The cluster has begun to meet quarterly to share updates and collaboration opportunities, and in fact has already produced a few outputs. SmartCHANGE's first webinar and accompanying post-event report was on the legal and ethical aspects of AI and was done in collaboration with AI4HF and DT4H. The cluster has additionally conducted a shared workshop at the Health Data Summit 25, which the SmartCHANGE project helped organize,

though unfortunately it was unable to participate in due to unforeseen circumstances. As all the projects in the cluster enter into the second phase and more results become available, we expect collaboration opportunities to increase in both frequency and depth. The cluster will additionally consider expanding its membership where relevant. The clustering activities will continue to serve the high-level objectives identified in the previous iteration of this plan, which are:

- Driving joint dissemination via synergy formations
- Organising co-hosted events
- Publishing of success stories
- Co-creating of policy briefs
- Engaging with the EC on priorities

SmartCHANGE is currently identifying organisations, initiatives and associations, amongst others, from different stakeholder types, to align and work on common opportunities and goals. The synergies to be established as a result of this initial work will be aimed at increasing health literacy and awareness, providing better access to critical information by health professionals, provide interactive spaces to support dissemination of SmartCHANGE KERs and explore future opportunities for exploitation of the results.

The project has established a connection with the Science|Business magazine, which is renowned for being a platform that communicates exciting scientific news and developments to a wide range of stakeholders, ranging from policymakers to researchers to educators. The connection will not only enable further range for the communication and dissemination of the results, but can also provide a potential link for events and news.

All the consortium partners are being involved in this effort in all of its phases, helping to identify potential liaisons or facilitating contact with different organisations to create multiple, mutually beneficial relations which could take various forms such as organisation of joint events, acting as multipliers on dissemination and communication activities of interest to both, or authorship of joint papers/articles/news pieces and contribution to SmartCHANGE documents and adoption of results.

4.5 Community database

A community database has been setup for the SmartCHANGE project in a spreadsheet format. This database will be used for outreach (according to GDPR) and to keep track of all stakeholder engagement activities. The main element of reference for each contact will be

the Name and Surname, as it is the single element that is generally identifiable across all community entrance systems (newsletter, event participants, social media followers, synergies, and other collaborations, including the feasibility studies). We additionally aim to verify emails to avoid duplicates and to categorise them according to their stakeholder category so as to verify impact. The number of verified and relevant contacts will be incremented thanks to web platform registration and newsletter subscriptions, contacts from social media networks, participations at events, partners' efforts and synergies and strategic collaborations. The database is being exploited by SmartCHANGE to create awareness and consolidate a user base for the results. The retention of this data is described in the SmartCHANGE Privacy Policy. The final aim and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the community database is to reach 3000 contacts (number of contacts including registered users, social media, event participants, etc.) by the end of the project (see Table 7).

4.6 Monitoring and assessment

Evaluation of the Communication and Marketing activities is based on regular KPIs tracking, monitoring the dissemination, communication, papers submission and presence/organisation at events. Trackers are built based on the reporting forms available on the EC funding and tenders portal entry point for participants in funded projects. By using them as a benchmark and with feedback after the first reporting period, we've smoothed the reporting process and ensure that the communication and dissemination activities are properly reported.

An online visual Dashboard has also been setup to measure the online presence and the community engagement in real-time, as well as allowing visualisation of trends and comparing performance over time of the SmartCHANGE website and social media channels. The communication and dissemination KPIs are listed in Table 7.

Table 7 – Communication and Dissemination KPIs

#	Communication and Dissemination measure	Reason	Target KPI
1	Organisation of conferences/workshops	Raising awareness and increasing number of adopters	Number of events organised: 10 events (physical) with 150 visitors, including two demo days for non-specialised audiences

2	Organisation of common events with affiliated projects	Strategic synergies	Number of common events organised: 4 events (physical, as part of #1)
3	Attendance to third-party conferences/workshops	Increase visibility and adoption rate of SmartCHANGE	Number of events attended: 30 events (online or physical)
4	Common activities with affiliated projects: white papers OR joint videos, OR joint policy recommendations	Strategic synergies	4 (1 per year)
5	Number of people using the SmartCHANGE apps	Increase adopters from healthcare professionals and families	200 children and youth and a comparable number of family members; 20 healthcare professionals.
6	Promotional campaigns for proof-of-concept studies	Use the studies as early adopters and increase the adoption rate	Number of campaigns including press releases, newsletters, videos, social media promotion etc.: 4 (1 per country)
7	Online webinars directed to the general public	Increase visibility	4 with 80 attendees
8	Open access reports: number of scientific publications	Technical dissemination	10 journals, 20 conferences plus 5 non-scientific publications in industry magazines
9	Standardisation liaisons: common publications	Strategic synergies	3 contributions to standards / associations
10	Overall SmartCHANGE community	Community building	Number of contacts including registered users, social media, event participants, etc.: 3000
11	Project website: overall sessions	Community building	500 per month (by m48)

12	Promotional videos	Increase visibility, attract customers and adopters	15 videos
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5 Conclusions and next steps

Building on the foundation established in [D8.2], this midterm report highlights significant progress in implementing SmartCHANGE's communication and dissemination strategies while outlining concrete pathways for the remaining lifecycle of the project.

The project has successfully established a solid communication strategy, including a well-maintained website, active social media channels, and a growing stakeholder community. Our participatory design approach has proven effective in engaging target audiences and will be further reinforced as proof-of-concept studies advance.

Looking ahead, **communication** efforts will intensify with expanded multimedia production, including demo videos and user testimonials. Social media outreach will evolve with our new Instagram account, complementing our established presence on LinkedIn and YouTube. **Dissemination** activities will become increasingly results-driven, with a stronger presence at third-party events to showcase findings from proof-of-concept studies. The upcoming Healthy Lifestyle Tours will offer a direct channel to engage the public and promote awareness around lifestyle and NCD prevention.

Stakeholder engagement remains central, with tailored strategies for health professionals, families, and policymakers. Insights from ongoing studies will refine our outreach, ensuring alignment with real-world needs. KPI-based monitoring (e.g. community growth, event participation) will continue guiding adaptive improvements across all communication and engagement activities.

On the side of **exploitation**, which was covered in the first C&D plan (D8.2), the upcoming months (until M29) will focus on finalising the mobile and web applications, supported by technical documentation and pilot testing with healthcare partners. The Initial Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D8.5, due M30) will define pathways for long-term adoption, while the Stay Healthy Cluster will help amplify visibility and build cross-project synergies.

This remains a living strategy, designed to evolve as the project progresses. Final versions of the Dissemination & Communication Plan [D8.4] and Exploitation & Sustainability Plan [D8.6] will be delivered at M48. By maintaining this dynamic, impact-focused approach, SmartCHANGE is poised to maximise its scientific, social, and commercial legacy in AI-driven health innovation.

6 References

Although the adopted style for references in the SmartCHANGE project is the Name-Year style, an exception is made in the case of this document, since it references only relevant deliverables of the project itself, with no external references involving third-party authors. This exception is made for reasons of clarity and brevity.

The following deliverables are referenced in this document:

[D1.1] “Project Handbook”. M3 (July 2023).

[D1.2] “Data Management Plan”, M6 (October 2023).

[D2.1] “Benchmark of regulatory and ethical frameworks”. M6 (October 2023).

[D8.1] “Project Website”. M6 (October 2023).

[D8.3] “Midterm dissemination and communication report and plan”. M24 (April 2025)

[D8.4] “Final dissemination and communication report and plan”. M48 (April 2027)

[D8.5] “Initial exploitation and sustainability plan”. M30 (October 2025)

[D8.6] “Final exploitation and sustainability plan”. M48 (April 2027)

[D8.7] “Networking and clustering report”. M45 (January 2027)